

D1.2

Data Management Plan

Revision v2.0 finalised in 2026

Initial version:

Work package	WP1
Task	T1.4
Due date	30-06-2023
Submission date	22-06-2023
Deliverable lead	ESF
Version	V1.3
Authors	Mariette Vandermersch-Desmartin (ESF)
Reviewers	Emmanuel Destis (ESF), Miguel Garcia (SPLORO), Raquel Carro (AUSTRALO)

Abstract

This document outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for data collected, generated and processed by the NGI Sargasso project. The document is following the FAIR data management guidelines and adhere to RRI's open access policy. It provides the initial description of research data and its management.

Keywords

NGI Sargasso, Data Management, Data Collection, Data Storage, EU, Next Generation Internet.

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v1.1	26-05-2023	1 st version of deliverable template	Mariette Vandermersch-Desmartin (ESF)
V1.2	30-05-23	Correction	Emmanuel Detsis (ESF)
V1.3	16-06-23	Correction	Miguel Garcia (SPLORO), Raquel Carro (AUSTRALO), Teresa Barber (MWCB)
V1.4	01-12-25	Update	Mariette Vandermersch-Desmartin (ESF)
V2.0	04-02-26	Update	Mariette Vandermersch-Desmartin (ESF)

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are provided by the NGI Sargasso project's consortium under EC grant agreement 01092887 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice

This deliverable is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC_BY). This means that you are free to share, copy, distribute, and adapt the content of this deliverable for any purpose, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original authors and provide a link to the CC_BY license.

<i>Project co-funded by the European Commission in the HORIZON EUROPE Programme</i>	
<i>Nature of the deliverable</i>	R
<i>Dissemination level</i>	
<i>PU</i>	Public, fully open. e.g., website ✓
<i>CL</i>	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC
<i>CO</i>	Confidential to GENOMED4ALL project and Commission Services

*** Deliverable types:**

- R:** document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).
- DEM:** demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.
- DEC:** websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER:** software, technical diagrams, etc.

Table of contents

Introduction	6
Data Summary.....	7
Existing Data to reuse	7
New data.....	7
Fair Data	17
Making data findable.....	17
Making data accessible.....	17
Making data interoperable.....	19
Increase data re-use.....	19
Other research outputs.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Allocation of resources.....	19
Data security	19
Ethics.....	20
Protection of Personal Data.....	21
Non-EU Countries.....	22
Annex 1 – Formats and names	23
General guidelines for selecting file formats.....	23
General guidelines for naming the files.....	23
Annex 2 – Datasets.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.

Abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
NGI	New Generation Internet
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
DPO	Data Protection Officer
WP	Work Package
US	United States
CA	Canada

Introduction

This document outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for data collected, generated and processed by the NGI Sargasso project. The document is following the FAIR data management guidelines and adhere to RRI's open access policy. It provides the initial description of research data and its management.

The ethical and legal issues related to management of personal data and informed consent within the project are covered by the NGI SARGASSO Ethics Framework, consisting of the DMP and its updates, plus the Project Handbook and Ethics deliverables, which detail the duties and obligations of the Consortium partners to ensure the project's compliance with current legislative frameworks.

Data Summary

NGI Sargasso generated a certain amount of research data during its execution.

Moreover, the project involved carrying out **data collection**, including personal data and metadata (in context of the internal personal data of the consortium partners but specially the personal data of the applicants in the frame of our open calls and when they will be joining our public events).

Existing Data to reuse

NGI Sargasso relied on previously produced data that will be obtained through data scrapping and recruitment repositories, as well as desktop research for literature review. Some other data will come from partners' own databases. This data was of text and numerical nature.

Examples:

- The ESF college of experts mailing list has been used to send an email disseminating the NGI SARGASSO project.
 - Saved on the ESF SmartSimple secured Platform
 - The data saved on this mailing list are the name, email and expertise of the ESF college of experts
- MWCB used its internal list of experts to find coaches

New data

The project produced large amount of text, audiovisual and numerical data through all the interviews, surveys, workshops, project pilots, focus groups and data scrapping planned.

AUSTRALO

AUSTRALO leads the Communication and Dissemination Work Package of NGI SARGASSO and is responsible for the development, management and monitoring of all project communication assets and related datasets.

Within the WP it generated much audiovisual data:

- The development and continuous update of the [NGI SARGASSO website](#), serving as the central information hub for the project and its open calls.
- The design and publication of original visual and editorial content (posts, visuals, promotional graphics, announcements) disseminated through LinkedIn, Mastodon and other relevant platforms.
- The production and publication of beneficiary interviews and project videos on the [NGI SARGASSO Youtube Channel](#), enhancing visibility of funded projects and showcasing impact stories.
- The creation of event-related communication materials (posters, flyers, stickers, roll-ups, videos), distributed and displayed during conferences, brokerage events, workshops and international forums to strengthen outreach and stakeholder engagement.
- A Stakeholder Collaboration Framework to identify existing networks, initiatives and resources to nurture synergies and strategic alliances and relationships over the long-term as well as promote the project open calls.

TABLE 1: DATASET 1.A. STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

Datatype name	Stakeholder Collaboration Framework
Data description	This data includes relevant networks and initiatives (DIHs, associations), projects, and resources (National Contact Points, publication platforms, social media profiles) relevant for the objectives of the project.
File type	Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to make possible the identification of existing networks, initiatives and resources to nurture synergies and strategic alliances and relationships over the long-term as well as promote the project open calls.

They have created a mailing list of the Newsletter subscribers.

TABLE 2: DATASET 1.B. NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIBERS

Datatype name	Newsletter Subscribers
Data description	This dataset includes the email and name of the subscribers.
File type	Excel

Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to send the quarterly newsletter with updated information on the project developments and opportunities.
Data provider	Brevo (platform compliant with all data and GDPR regulations: https://www.brevo.com/legal/termsofuse/)

They have created a database of American contacts (National contact points, NSF grantees, academics, publication platforms) to provide information about our calls, webinars, meetings, and brokerage services.

TABLE 3: DATABASE 1.C. AMERICAN CONTACTS

Datatype name	American contacts
Data description	This dataset includes the email and first name of the subscribers.
File type	Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to provide information about our calls, webinars, meetings, and brokerage services to American (US and CA) contacts
Data provider	NSF database of grantees

Finally, they have created a list of relevant events to the NGI Sargasso projects

TABLE 4: DATABASE 1.D. EVENTS MONITORING

Datatype name	Events monitoring
Data description	This dataset includes the event type, the name of the event, its description, location and date, and the name of the NGI Sargasso partners participating.
File type	Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to identify relevant events organised in the frame of the New Generation Internet and collect the participation of NGI Sargasso members to those events.

SPLORO

SPLORO is in charge of the Open Call WP and thus collected:

- The potential and selected evaluators personal information: Name, surname, Gender, Country of origin, legal address, ID number, e-mail, bank account, CV, area of expertise (select from technologies), previous experience evaluating cascade funding projects, previous experience evaluating NGI, motivation to evaluate NGI Sargasso and previous expertise evaluating USA-Canada-EU initiatives. Those data have been collected via the Calls for Evaluators that have been organised before each cut-off date from Call 1 to Call 4.
- The applicants information: Name, surname, e-mail, legal and short name of organization, type of organization, address, VAT number, PIC number, phone number, website address, bank details, legal signatory details
- The applicant's projects: title, abstract, their answer to the application form specially generated for the NGI SARGASSO project, the contact name of their US/Canadian partner.

SPLORO is also the owner of the brokerage platform dataset, containing potential applicants information, which has been used for matchmaking activities but also to send surveys and information about the calls.

SPLORO finally generated new data via the creation of guidelines for the applicants, videos and, tutorials, that are notably available on the project website as well as on the [NGI SARGASSO Youtube Channel](#).

TABLE 5: DATASET 2.A: OPEN CALL DATASET

Datatype name	Open Call Dataset
Data description	Contains information about the entities selected in the open calls, including details about the entity and the team, progress data in the added-value services program, and others.
File type	The data is collected and stored in structured digital format. It includes textual information such as company profiles, team details, etc. The format is electronic, with the data being entered and managed in the Sploro platform. This was downloaded as excel files for the reporting phase.
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to collect information on the companies selected in the open calls . This data includes basic information on the company and the team, the content of the applications, and similar details. The main objective is to analyse, monitor and evaluate the beneficiaries of the open call. This data contributes to assess the

Data provider	effectiveness and impact of the project and its support to the participating enterprises.
	<p>SPLORO.</p> <p>The data is collected from applicants who submit a proposal via the Sploro platform. Data is collected and consolidated by the leader of the evaluation process. Communication channels with applicants are defined in the “Guidelines for Applicants”. All the information related to competitive calls <u>havehas</u> been exported to the project repository to enable the long-term storage and access to data by consortium members and auditors. SPLORO exported all applications from the Sploro portal to the project repository.</p>

TABLE 6: DATASET 2.B. OPEN CALL FOR EXTERNAL EVALUATORS DATASET

Datatype name	Open Call for external evaluators Dataset
Data description	<p>Contains information from external experts that will be involved in multiple evaluation tasks during the NGI Sargasso.</p> <p>This is an original dataset to be created in the context of WP3 because of the competitive call (“open call”) procedure.</p>
File type	<p>Several types of data: documents, emails, texts etc.</p> <p>The data will be collected and stored in structured digital format. It may include textual information such as company profiles, team details, and progress reports, as well as quantitative data such as KPIs and performance metrics. The format will primarily be electronic, with the data being entered and managed in the Sploro platform.</p>
Purpose of the data	<p>The purpose of this dataset is to manage the contractual relationship between experts and the consortium. Also facilitates the selection and assessment of evaluators through an efficient and safeguarded process. This data will include details such as the evaluators' profile, contact information, professional experience, and expertise. The aim is to match the evaluators to the specific needs and requirements of the submitted proposals to carry out a proper evaluation.</p>
Data provider	<p>SPLORO.</p> <p>The availability of external experts will be collected through a form on the Sploro portal by submitting their expression of interest and areas of</p>

expertise. Contracts and related documents of the selected evaluators, such as statements of honour, receipts and other expense information, will be submitted in a form on the Sploro portal or by email.

TABLE 7: DATASET 2.C. BROKERAGE PLATFORM DATASET

Datatype name	Open Call Dataset
Data description	Contains information about the entities registered in the brokerage system including details about the entity and the team, domain of expertise, etc
File type	The data is collected and stored in structured digital format. It includes textual information such as company profiles, team details, etc. The format is electronic, with the data being entered and managed in the Sploro platform. This was downloaded as excel files
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to do matchmakings between the registered entities and allow them to find partners to submit a proposal, but also to send surveys and information about the calls.
Data provider	<p>SPLORO.</p> <p>The data is collected from applicants who submit a proposal via the Sploro platform.</p>

MWCB

MWCB organised matchmaking events that worked as info sessions as well as allowed European teams to meet potential partners and vice-versa. Thus, MWCB created a dataset of the participants that attended the online events.

They also collected several information from the granted applicants: Name, Surname, company, position, email of the contact person, detail of their project, ambitions and KPI's, and answer to the satisfaction surveys, among others, with the aim to have a follow up of their mentoring process and evolution.

MWCB collected information about their mentors and speakers: their personal information have been processed by MWCB (Name, Surname, company, position, email of the contact person and results)

Finally, MWCB generated new data via the creation of training material for the successful participants (powerpoint presentation, etc).

TABLE 8: DATASET 3.A. MATCHMAKING PARTICIPANTS DATASET

Datatype name	Matchmaking participants datasets
Data description	The dataset includes (but is not limited to): Contact details (name, email, address), country of origin, Area of Knowledge interest, Baseline technology, type of organization
File type	Personal contact information, pitch deck (ppt) and documentation of project and research.
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to successfully pair teams so that they can apply to the NGI Sargasso open calls. Internal use: MWCB will analyse the data, results of analysis will feed into open calls. External use: MWCB will share this information among all participants, allowing participants to contact their matched team.
Data provider	Airmeet and Sploro Platform (Accelerator App) will be used as platforms to collect that. A form is created so they can submit their expression of interest.

TABLE 9: 3.B. SUBGRANTEES DATASET

Datatype name	SubGrantees dataset
Data description	The dataset includes (but is not limited to): Contact details (name, email, address), country of origin, Baseline technology, type of organization, KPIs and Milestones, etc
File type	Personal contact information, pitch deck (ppt) and documentation of project and research.
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to follow up the fulfilment of the deliverables and milestones for each stage for each grantee.

TABLE 10: DATASET 3.C. MENTORS AND SPEAKERS DATASETS

Datatype name	Mentors and speakers datasets
Data description	The dataset includes (but is not limited to): Contact details (name, email, address), professional experience, expertise, and financial details (Bank details, financial representative details (name, email and direct phone number)), contracts, payments request, proof of payments, amendments, their answer to the different surveys submitted and the answer of the surveys answered by the subgrantees.
File type	The data is collected, managed and stored in excel.
Purpose of the data	<p>The purpose of collecting personal information about the mentors of the programme is to facilitate effective mentorship and support for the participating entities. The objective is to match the mentors with the specific needs and requirements of the beneficiary companies, enabling personalized guidance and mentorship throughout the programme.</p> <p>The information also assists in monitoring and evaluating the mentors' contributions and impact on the beneficiary entities' progress. Access to this dataset should be restricted to authorized project personnel and handled in accordance with data protection regulations to maintain privacy and confidentiality.</p>
Data provider	Airmeet Accelerator App - information have been collected through desk research and potentially a form on the Sploro portal by submitting their expression of interest.

ESF

ESF generated new data via the realisation of interviews and surveys. All the data (mainly text) are saved on the project internal depository – SharePoint. Access to data was managed on a need-to-access basis and restricted to specific roles and partners.

ESF is also in charge of the payment of the application evaluators and the distribution of the Cascade Funding. In order to do the transfers, a contract was signed with each of them. The following data was collected:

- The Selected Evaluators: Name, Address, Bank details, financial representative details (name, email and direct phone number),
- The Successful Applicants: Name, Address of the main contact, Organisation contacts details, Bank details, legal representative details, financial representative details

(name, email and direct phone number), as well as the KPI's defined with MWCB and the different steps of application.

ESF took minutes of all the NGI Sargasso meetings, which produced text documents saved on the project repository (SharePoint).

Finally, ESF generated financial reporting for the EC.

TABLE 11: 4.A. INTERVIEWS AND SURVEYS RESULTS

Datatype name	Interviews and surveys results
Data description	Selected experts contact details (name, email, position, detailed expertise) and their answers to interviews and surveys questions This dataset includes their answers to several questions generated by ESF.
File type	Word, Excel and PowerPoint reports
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database was to define the challenges for the NGI SARGASSO calls thanks to the expertise of selected NGI experts and the inputs collected from the community, which allowed to receive applications corresponding to the needs of the NGI community.
Data provider	Experts

TABLE 12: DATASET 4.B. EVALUATORS DATASET

Datatype name	Evaluators dataset
Data description	The dataset includes Contact details (name, email, address) and financial details (Bank details, financial representative details (name, email and direct phone number)), contracts, payments request, proof of payments, amendments,
File type	PDF Documents, Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to manage the contractual relationship and the payment process between the evaluators, and NGI Sargasso

Data provider	Contact information is be collected through a form on the Sploro portal by submitting their expression of interest and application. Contracts, invoices and payment related documents are stored in the project repository
---------------	--

TABLE 13: DATASET 4.C. SUB-GRANTEES DATASET

Datatype name	Subgrantees dataset
Data description	The dataset includes Contact details from the main applicant, the additional contacts and the organisation granted (name, email, address, legal signatory details) and financial details (Bank details, financial representative details (name, email and direct phone number)), grant agreement, payment documents, proof of payments, amendments, etc
File type	PDF Documents, Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this dataset is to manage the contractual relationship and the payment process between the sub-grantees and NGI Sargasso
Data provider	Contact is collected through a form on the Sploro portal by submitting their application. Extra legal information and financial information (bank details, etc) are collected through a form on ESF side once selected. Contracts and payment related documents are stored in the project repository

TABLE 14: DATASET 4.D. FINANCIAL REPORTING

Datatype name	Financial reporting
Data description	Detail of the expenses of each beneficiaries
File type	Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to produce the financial reporting to the EC and justify the use of the funds corresponding to each WP.
Data provider	ESF

TABLE 15: DATASET 4.E. OPEN CALL CHALLENGES DATABASE

Datatype name	Financial reporting
Data description	Detail of which challenges were addressed in proposed and selected projects for Open Call 1-5.
File type	Excel
Purpose of the data	The purpose of this database is to assess which challenges were proposed and addressed by projects in each Open Call. It was used in open Call 4 and 5 to select the list of challenges for these calls.
Data provider	ESF

Fair Data

NGI SARGASSO seeks to make research data available on an open access basis where possible in line with the expectations of the Open Research Data Pilot.

ESF is responsible for data management and quality assurance as leader of task T1.4 Data Management. The associated costs are included in the project management budget (WP1).

Making data findable

Each dataset created as part of the project is evaluated by the content owners of the dataset and categorized as **1) open, 2) embargoed, or 3) restricted**.

The category appears on top of each document.

Datasets are stored in the participating organisations' databases, and/or in the SPLORO Accelerator app, and/or repositories and in the NGI Sargasso SharePoint created as the partners' internal database.

Making data accessible

Datasets and deliverables categorized as open or embargoed are **made publicly available** (after the embargo period has expired in the case of an embargo) through the **public section of the project website** (<https://ngisargasso.eu/repository/>) and **ZENODO** (https://zenodo.org/communities/ngisargasso_horizoneu/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest), as it gives each data uploaded a unique persistent, digital object identifier (DOI) and the institutional repositories.

Internally, all data are made available for review and reusable from the partners unless the task leader can justify why the data cannot be made openly available.

All data deposited on ZENODO is available to the public without restriction.

For other data, potential users must contact the IPR team or the data owner to gain access. If necessary, an appropriate IPR procedure (e.g., a non-disclosure agreement) will be used.

Making data interoperable

Partners are considering [OpenAIRE guidelines](#) for Literature, institutional, and thematic Repositories, for Data Archives, for CRIS Managers and the guidelines drafts for Software Repository Managers and for Other Research Products.

NGI Sargasso consortium also ensures its data follows the [guidelines for FAIR data under Horizon Europe open-access policy](#) and commit to any possible update in these guidelines.

To ensure interoperability, all datasets will use the same standards for the collection and/or creation of data and metadata as the project progresses and more data is identified and collected.

Increase data re-use

Data and other research outputs are shared through Creative Common Licensing, and are made explicit how research data/other outputs may be reused.

Open access research data will be licensed under an Attribution (CC-BY) or Universal (CC0) license, while any raw data produced will present a Creative Commons Public Domain Mark.

When possible, information and documentation on tools, software and/or models used for validation of the research and for data generation, interpretation and reuse will also be made available, to guarantee data reuse and validation.

Allocation of resources

Costs related to the research data curation, hosting and storage (institutional servers, cloud services, etc.) are covered from the partners' institutional budgets and/or overheads and therefore not charged as direct costs to the project. Each partner bears the responsibility for managing their research data.

Data security

Partners who provide data will perform the required quality assessment at their home institutions according to their own security and quality protocols. For data shared between

consortium partners, the main repository is the ESF Sharepoint attributed to NGI Sargasso. The ESF sharepoint is based on Microsoft Office 365 suit of products, with the main servers in France and Ireland. The project repository is accessed via password login to the MS sharepoint servers and only consortium partners that have been identified as “need to access” have received the required authorisation.

All relevant data are deposited at least in one open-access repository. See “Making data accessible” section for more details.

The project website acts to house a description of available project data.

Guidelines that are followed and implemented by partners to limit the risk of data leaks:

- Keep pseudonymised personal data of respondents and the code keys separate;
- Encrypt data when necessary;
- Store data in separate locations to avoid loss of data;
- Limit the use of flash drives;
- Save files in one of the preferred formats (see Annex 1)
- Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset (see Annex 1)

Ethics

The Data Management is done in full compliance with any European and national legislation relevant to the country where the data collections are taking place.

Best practice principles that set the baseline to be followed in all cases:

Personally identifiable data will:

- Be collected only with the explicit, fully informed consent and voluntary agreement of the research participants.
- Not be sold
- Not be collected for purposes beyond project aims
- Be collected only as strictly necessary for completion of the study
- Be deleted, if it was collected unintentionally (for example, data shadow)

Protection of Personal Data

NGI SARGASSO research and project activities involves non-EU countries (US and Canada).

As a policy, no transfers from non-EU countries to the EU (or another third state), is taking place without the **data subjects' explicit agreement**.

All recruited experts were experienced and fully knowledgeable about the ethical issues involved, and will accordingly comply with all local statutory and regulatory requirements covering personal data transfer.

In accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 transfers from EU countries to a non-EU country or international organisations only took place on the following conditions:

- With the data subjects' explicit and informed consent to such a transfer
- At the data subject's request, if the transfer is necessary for the performance of a contract. In addition, in situations where adequacy decision or appropriate safeguards are absent, information about the possible risks of such transfers will be included.

In the conduct of the study, partners had to observe the following principles of responsibility toward research participants:

- Respecting the integrity and dignity of persons
- Voluntary nature of participation
- Provision of information on the context of the study
- Provision of a project information sheet
- The right to withdraw from the study
- Anonymity
- Respecting the principle of proportionality
- Not to impose more than necessary on the participants, as well as not going beyond stated objectives
- Considering the concerns research raises and building an understanding that all benefits of this research are for the good of society
- Protection from harm and discomfort

For informed consent procedures, the minimum approach to prepare the information sheets and consent forms is accordingly set as: *Any and all subjects participating in the research as data sources will be informed about the project, the data collection and its further use.*

Prior to their involvement in data gathering processes, research participants will be asked to sign the *Informed Consent Form* which will contain clear information on:

- the aims, purpose, methods and implications of the research
- who is organising and funding the project and for what purpose
- who will benefit from the research

- the expected duration of the subject's participation with an estimate of the time and effort expected of participants
- degree of benefit, risks, burden or discomfort involved in participation
- participation is voluntary and upon invitation
- a statement offering the subject the opportunity to ask questions and to withdraw their consent at any time from the research without consequences
- precautions to ensure participants' safety and provide information on insurance, if there is any
- the commitment to protect respondents' anonymity and privacy and explanation of the extent to which it can be guaranteed
- clear commitment to treating personal and sensitive information confidentially.
- secure procedures for analysing data gathered.
- who will have access to any data that participants provide.
- incidental findings and how they will be dealt with.
- a reference to whom to contact for answers to pertinent questions about the research and research subjects' rights.

In addition to the above, and in line with the GDPR and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, research participants will be provided with detailed information about the envisaged data processing of their personal data in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language.

The minimum info here is set at:

- the identity of the data controller and, where applicable, the contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO),
- the specific purpose(s) of the processing for which the personal data will be used,
- the subject's rights, in particular:
 - the right to withdraw consent or access their data o the procedures to follow should they wish to do so
 - the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority o information as to whether data will be shared with or transferred to third parties and for what purposes
- how long the data will be retained before they are destroyed

Non-EU Countries

There were no transfer of data to Non-EU Countries from NGI Sargasso project partners, but there were some compulsory transfer of information between the granted teams themselves, for the purpose of the development and execution of their projects

Annex 1 – Formats and names

General guidelines for selecting file formats

NGI SARGASSO takes measures to prevent future file format obsolescence by giving preference to file formats with high chances of remaining usable in the future. In general, such formats should be:

- commonly used
- have open specifications
- independent of specific software, developers or suppliers.

Formats meeting these criteria are best suited for long-time preservation and accessibility.

Formats may not always cover all desired attributes. File formats used can be divided into preferred formats (ideal cases offering best chances for usability and accessibility) and acceptable formats (formats meeting the bare minimum required).

NGI SARGASSO uses the formats listed below.

File format type:	Preferred	Acceptable
Text docs	.doc	.odt
Spreadsheets	.xls	.csv; .ods

General guidelines for naming the files

All the NGI Sargasso files are labelled in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the coherence of the final dataset : NGI SARGASSO_category_name of the document

Example: Deliverable are labelled NGI SARGASSO_DX.X_Name of the deliverable

For other documents (draft versions, of deliverables, meeting minutes, etc) The document name ends with the date of the event (when relevant) using the following format: dd.mm.yy

